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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

D12.1 Data Management Plan

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Prepared By:	Roland Kunert
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Terms, Definitions and Abbreviated Terms

CA	Consortium Agreement
DMP	Data Management Plan
GA	Grant Agreement
WP / WPL	Work Package / Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

The data management strategy and detailed data management plan (DMP), part of Task 12.1/13.1, for making their data/research outputs findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) will be laid out by this document for the first time and revised at 6 monthly intervals. The DMP covers the data management life cycle for all data sets that will be collected, processed, and generated by the project during the project and beyond, and includes the exceptions for open research data. The DMP considers the following:

- Data collection/creation
- Appraisal and selection
- Documentation and metadata
- File formats
- Storage
- Copyright and intellectual property.

This document is the first version of the DMP and it is prepared in compliance with the template provided by the Commission: “Data management plan (HE): V1.1 – 01.04.2022”¹.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

2. Introduction

The document provides a detailed overview of how data will be managed throughout the APOLLO project. It covers the entire data life cycle, including collection, processing, and generation, as well as methodologies and standards to be adhered to. Additionally, it outlines plans for sharing the data, whether it will be made open, and the strategies for curating and preserving it.

The scientific objectives for the APOLLO project are as follows:

Current recycling practices for photovoltaic (PV) waste modules are primitive, resulting in low-volume, low-value materials. This undermines economic viability and sustainability goals, as efficient recovery of all constituents at a suitable quality for reuse in new PVs is essential with minimal environmental impact. In this context, the EU-funded **APOLLO project** will establish a circular approach, efficiently recovering all constituents for reuse in new PVs. Innovative techniques increase weight recovery. Recycled silicon will be used for new ingots, cells, and modules. A pilot line will process 40 tonnes of PV waste, producing materials for 1 tonne of remanufactured silicon and 30 exemplar PV modules. These modules will incorporate new designs, materials, and manufacturing methods, and be designed for disassembly and recycling.

The project is structure in the following technical work packages (WPs):

- WP1 Assessment, Disassembly and Streaming
- WP2 Material Separation and Assessment
- WP3 Optimised Sonification and Assessment
- WP4 Material Refinement and Assessment
- WP5 Material Remanufacture
- WP6 Future PV Design and Manufacture
- WP7 PV Passports and Marketplace Concept
- WP8 PV Passport and Marketplace Implementation
- WP9 PV Recycling Pilot Line
- WP10 Baselines and Priorities: Environmental and Circular Business Modelling
- WP11 Implementation and Analysis of Environmental and Circular Model Benefits

To facilitate the technical work, there are also non-technical work packages to coordinate all the work packages, disseminate and communicate project results and to ensure compliance with the ethics requirements:

- WP12 Exploitation and Communication (P1)
- WP13 Exploitation and Communication (P2)
- WP14 Project Management (P1)
- WP15 Project Management (P1)

3. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

3.1 Making Data Findable

All non-confidential data generated within the framework of the APOLLO project will be published in an open-access format. With that, a digital object identifier (DOI) will be assigned together with commonly used metadata, such as:

- Author(s) information
- Title
- Date of publication
- Author(s) organization(s)
- Journal or name of the platform
- Issue volume and pages (if applicable)
- Grant project name, acronym and number
- Keywords

The metadata standards and contents will follow the rules and guidelines of the dedicated platform or journal. To improve the discoverability of the data, search keywords will be included.

Metadata of deposited data will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent.

3.2 Making Data Accessible

Externally, resources such as Zenodo will be employed for open access of APOLLO data and results, such as Si refinement purity and process, glass analysis data sets, PV passport analysis, PV recycling efficacy and so on. As an open-format tool Zenodo, for example, has little limit on the type, format or size of data, giving easy accessibility and flexibility, and submissions can be controlled by the organisation submitting them.

Partners may also use open data repositories provided by their institute, university or company, on which the relevant metadata will also be available, and which will also have a DOI and a link to the APOLLO project persistent link.

Rules which are laid out in the GA and CA are in place and are specifically described in the GA, Annex 5, Article 17 and CA, sec. 8.4. In the latter it is specified that **for confidential information** (see CA, sec. 10): “During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the [described] procedure [...]” “Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other

Parties at least **30 calendar days before the publication**. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination without undue delay, at latest within 20 calendar days after receipt of the notice.”

All data published will use a license according to the principle ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’. This will be most likely the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights².

Each partner is responsible to upload the data on the repository of choice and to link the DOI corresponding to the data to the persistent link of the APOLLO project on the Horizon Europe website³.

3.3 Making Data Interoperable

The partners of the APOLLO project will use data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats and methodologies which follow the general practices within the scientific community. This consistency is expected to make the data generated in the project interoperable and flexible for exchange across disciplines.

3.4 Making Data Re-usable

Together with openly published data, variable definitions, information on methodology, units of measurement and other information will be provided to ensure easy re-use of the data. Wherever possible, such information will be given within the header information of separately (e.g. in readme-files).

Reviews before publication will check the data for consistency.

² See also: <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/ccllicenses/>

³ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101122277>

4. APOLLO Project: Website, Server, Storage & Access

4.1 Website

The APOLLO website was set up with project start in January 2024 with the URL: <https://www.apolloproject.eu>. The website is used for storing only public documents related to the project and dissemination. The partner FENIX, task leader for T13.1 “Dissemination and Communication Activities”, is responsible for design, maintenance and regular update. The project provides both static information, including its overarching goal, funding information, and the consortium involved, as well as dynamic updates such as news, events, and publications, which are refreshed on a regular basis. This combination ensures that visitors receive both foundational details and the latest developments within the project, fostering engagement and keeping stakeholders informed.

4.2 Server, Storage & Access

An **owncloud solution**, hosted by Fraunhofer, was set up for data exchange and storage. Access is restricted to project members and credentials are managed by the Coordinator.

All partners are responsible for storing (confidential) information in connection with the APOLLO project, provided by others or produced by themselves, safe and secure. Fraunhofer and the division carrying out the work, as an example, is running an information security management system (ISMS) based on the international standard ISO/IEC 27001. The ISMS also meets the data protection provisions stipulated in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the German Federal Data Protection Act (Bundesdatenschutzgesetz, BDSG) by taking into account the requirements for technical and organizational measures specified in ISO/IEC 27701.

For easy access and working jointly on documents, also a **MS-Teams solution** is provided by Fraunhofer. This also allows the set up of ad-hoc and regular meetings. Contracts between Fraunhofer and Microsoft are in place to ensure that usage of MS-Teams is data protection compliant. Among other things, this means that contract have been set up with Microsoft Ireland Operations Ltd., Dublin/Ireland instead of Microsoft USA, resulting that the service provided, underlies European law in general and the general data protection regulation (Datenschutz Grundverordnung, DSGVO) in particular. However, the Coordinator emphasizes that confidential data should be exchanged with owncloud.

FIGURE 1: APOLLO WEBSITE: URL: [HTTPS://WWW.APOLLOPROJECT.EU](https://www.apolloproject.eu) (EXCERPT)

5. Conclusion

This report presents the initial release of the Data Management Plan for the APOLLO project, offering preliminary guidelines for managing project results both during and after the project's completion. It addresses aspects of data generation, storage, and sharing.

The report will be subject to changes and revisions according to the needs of the APOLLO project. According to the GA the publication of revised versions are planned in month 24 and 36.

6. References

[1] Persistent link to CORDIS: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101122277>

[2] Link to APOLLO website: <https://www.apolloproject.eu/>

7. Annex

7.1 Open Access

7.1.1 Golden Open Access

This type of open access publication refers to the primary publication of a scientific article in open access journal. As in conventional journals, here also a peer reviewed procedure is used. Main difference to conventional publication is: here, the author or his affiliating institute is charged with publication costs instead of the reader.

Meanwhile, the golden open access model is the typical, promoted way for scientific publication in most of the communities as well as in the framework of projects of the European commission.

7.1.2 Green Open Access

The parallel publication of articles in online repositories, before, after, or alongside its official publication, is referred to as green open access. The advantage using this publication type is the fast availability of the research data, which comes along with the disadvantage that only publications of post-prints have undergone a peer-review process.

This model is often promoted alongside the golden open access.

7.1.3 Open Access Research Data

Scientific findings in general and publications specifically rely on research data. Examples of these data are results of experiments, measurements, observations from fieldwork, and survey results. These (digital) data can be published, e.g. alongside with articles, on publicly accessible repositories.

